

PBMC viability (%)

			D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7
First experiment	Healthy donor 1 (1,0 million cells per well)	NS	89,4	83,3	82,5	80,1	77,9	75,6	63,4
First experiment	Healthy donor 1 (1,0 million cells per well)	PPD (1µg/ml)	92,7	83,8	81,3	76,8	74,7	76,4	68,2
First experiment	Healthy donor 1 (1,0 million cells per well)	SEB (100ng/ml)	86,8	79,4	71,6	57,1	38,9	37,0	31,5
Second experiment	Healthy donor 1 (1,0 million cells per well)	NS	82,3	82,7	ND	ND	78,6	ND	ND
Second experiment	Healthy donor 1 (0,5 million cells per well)	NS	75,0	76,9	ND	ND	79,3	ND	ND
Second experiment	Healthy donor 1 (1,0 million cells per well)	PPD (1µg/ml)	82,1	82,8	ND	ND	78,5	ND	ND
Second experiment	Healthy donor 1 (0,5 million cells per well)	PPD (1µg/ml)	74,9	75,0	ND	ND	74,1	ND	ND
Second experiment	Healthy donor 1 (1,0 million cells per well)	SEB (100ng/ml)	79,4	79,4	ND	ND	60,3	ND	ND
Second experiment	Healthy donor 1 (0,5 million cells per well)	SEB (100ng/ml)	74,1	75,8	ND	ND	67,2	ND	ND
Second experiment	Healthy donor 1 (1,0 million cells per well)	SEB (10ng/ml)	88,2	82,4	ND	ND	76,8	ND	ND
Second experiment	Healthy donor 1 (0,5 million cells per well)	SEB (10ng/ml)	74,8	79,3	ND	ND	71,7	ND	ND

ND: Not Determined